

Challenges, Coping Strategies, and Skills of Out-of-Field Physical Education Teachers as Mediated by Self-Efficacy

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to discern the challenges, coping strategies, and skills utilized by out-of-field teachers handling MAPEH subjects to determine self-efficacy mediates the relationship between the Challenges, coping strategies, and skills. The respondents rated moderate agreement on their challenges from initial to novice teachers. Moderate agreement assessment of the respondents on their challenges regarding ongoing teaching-learning. The assessment of the respondents as to the challenges they encountered in terms of professional development was verbally interpreted as moderately agree. The agreement from the respondents on their coping strategies utilized as to content knowledge. The respondents agreed that they utilize the indicated coping strategies. The respondents agreed that they utilized careful guidance as one of the strategies as out-of-field teachers. The respondents agreed on attentive leadership as a strategy for the out-of-field teacher. The assessment of the respondents on their human skills was verbally interpreted as agreeing. The hard skill is interpreted as agreed by the respondents.

The overall level of the respondents' performance in terms of self-efficacy is verbally interpreted as agreed. There is a significant relationship between coping strategies and self-efficacy variables. On the one hand, a moderate to strong relationship is seen between variables. Thus the research null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant relationship between coping strategies and performance variables. A moderate to strong relationship was seen between variables; hence, the research null hypothesis is partially sustained. Findings revealed that Self-Efficacy constructs do not mediate the relationship between Challenges and Performance. On the other hand, Self-Efficacy could explain the variations in Coping Strategies and Performance Scores. It led to the acceptance of the research null hypothesis.

KEYWORDS: Challenges, Coping Strategies, Human Skill, Hard Skill, Self-Efficacy

I. INTRODUCTION

Quality education is at the heart of sustainable development, acting as a powerful catalyst in developing more just, humane, and equitable societies. It has become critical in many rapidly increasing enrollments in many countries to achieve education for all. Education systems have recently been strained, but the assumption that there is a trade-off between access and quality is flawed. In countries with limited resources, successful efforts to increase access to primary education have frequently resulted in declining educational quality.

Also, education is essential in peoples' lives because it allows us to better our living conditions. To do so, people will need the help of others, specifically our teachers. The teacher's primary responsibility is to transfer knowledge and inspire students to learn more through experience. Teaching is a time-consuming endeavor. It is a multifaceted task regarded as the noblest of all professions because it lays the groundwork for any discipline that many people envision. As a result, their efforts are highly valued to begin the high-quality education that students deserve. Aside from their actions, teachers' educational backgrounds are essential in effective teaching. It is argued that a teacher is expected to demonstrate subject expertise.

To do justice to the preceding, people require the assistance of others, particularly teachers. The teacher's primary responsibility is to transfer knowledge and inspire students to learn more through experience. Teaching is a time-consuming endeavor. It is a multifaceted task regarded as the noblest of all professions because it lays the groundwork for any discipline that many people envision. As a result, their efforts are highly valued to begin the high-quality education that students deserve. Aside from their actions, teachers' educational backgrounds are important in effective teaching. It is argued that a teacher must demonstrate expertise in their subjects.

Du Plessis (2017) asserts that public school teachers play an essential role in society, particularly for students. Quality teachers are required for quality education. The availability of qualified teachers is critical in developing the educational system, as education quality is directly related to classroom instruction quality. Using qualified teachers in all schools is critical in

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improving student achievement. Teachers should be provided with the resources they need to perform their jobs professionally, such as subject matter knowledge and skills and teaching methodology. Teachers' competence has a significant impact on student performance. Furthermore, effective teachers have a broad understanding of their subjects and have frequently majored in those specialized areas (Villaberde, 2017).

The researcher obtained a degree majoring in MAPEH, which is why he handles the subject. However, his friends are hired but assigned to teach a subject out of their specialization. He believes that these teachers' ability to sing and dance was one of the reasons why they were allowed to teach MAPEH, even if it was out of their field of specialization. More so, the researcher notices that due to the lack of hired teachers with MAPEH majors, those specializing in other subjects such as Araling Panlipunan, Filipino, and others are tasked to teach the subject. They shared that they enjoy handling the subject, though there are instances, especially during the first few years, where they encountered hard times teaching the concepts and putting all those practices so that learners could grasp them. With this, the researcher would also like to examine the challenges and coping skills of those teaching MAPEH though the subject is not their specialization. The researcher believes that the pursuit of this study is significant in the field of teaching because of several reasons. First, the teachers asked to teach beyond their areas of expertise will be more motivated to improve their teaching. Second, the school-based management plan proposed by this study can be used to select better or manage teachers who are already in the position but given subject loads that are out of their specialization.

METHOD

This research study employed the participation of out-of-field physical education teachers in the division of Lipa City. The researcher utilized a sampling technique to include all out-of-field physical education teachers in this study. The number of respondents was taken from the 16 public high schools in the Lipa City division.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mean, and standard deviation was used to determine the challenges, coping strategies, and skills of out-of-field physical education teachers using a modified survey questionnaire. The same statistical treatment was to ascertain the respondents' self-efficacy level. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to identify the significant relationship between the challenges, coping strategies, and self-efficacy of the respondents and challenges, coping strategies, and performance. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to identify the relationship between self-efficacy mediates between challenges, coping strategies, and performance.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	29	29.0
Female	71	71.0
Total	100	100

It can be noticed from Table 2 that 71, which comprised 71 percent of the respondents, were female, whereas the remaining 29 or 29 percent were male. It can be said that women dominate teaching.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-25	16	16
26-30	39	39
31-35	22	22
36-40	10	9
41-45	8	8
46-50	5	5
51 and above	1	1
TOTAL	100	100

It can be seen from Table 2 that the majority of 39 percent, also composed of 39 respondents, were from the age bracket 26-30. Meanwhile, 22 percent or 22 respondents were from 31-35. The age brackets 20-25, 36-40, and 41-45 were represented by 16, 10, and eight (8) or 16 percent 9, and eight (8) percent of the respondents, respectively. Lastly, the ages 46-50 and 51 and above were represented by five (5) and one (1) respondent correspondingly. The results show that most respondents are still young in the teaching profession.

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Table 3. Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelors Degree	39	39.0
With Masteral Unit	20	20.0
Masters Degree	1	1.0
With Doctoral Units	40	40.0
Total	100	100

Of the 100 respondents, 39 percent or 39 attained their bachelor's degree as the highest form of education. On the one hand, the respondents with Master units were represented by 20 percent or 20 respondents. 40 respondents have doctoral units, while just one (1) attained a Masters's degree.

Table 4. Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Specialization

Specialization	Frequency	Percent
English	12	12.0
Mathematics	12	12.0
Social Science	17	17.0
MAPEH	9	9.0
Science	14	14.0
Values Education	11	11.0
Filipino	25	25.0
Total	100	100

It can be seen from Table 4 that majority of the respondents, which belonged to 25 percent of the sample, have Filipino as their area of specialization. Social and Science major teachers who are also teaching MAPEH were represented by 17 and 14 respondents, respectively. Both Mathematics and English areas of specialization have 12 respondents each. It can also be gleaned from the table that 14 and 11 teachers were given MAPEH subjects separately. Lastly, from the 100 respondents, only nine (9) have MAPEH as their field of expertise. It can be inferred that most of the teachers handling MAPEH subjects have attained out-of-field degrees. It suggests that there is a problem with the subject loading. It can be the case that each school only hires two to three MAPEH major teachers, despite a large number of students. According to the researcher's experience, non-major teachers who are assigned MAPEH as one of their teaching loads are merely expected to instruct the subjects to meet the minimum required number of hours or units for each teacher.

Table 5. Assessment of the Respondents on the Challenges Encountered in Terms of Transition from Initial Teacher to Novice

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Participating in the courses/workshops to improve my preparation for the lesson.	3.93	.946	Moderately Agree
delivering a more interactive lesson to my students	3.92	1.002	Moderately Agree
Integrating differentiated instruction in preparing my lesson.	3.90	1.000	Moderately Agree
providing technical assistance on students' behavior in the class	3.76	1.006	Moderately Agree
utilizing media-based instruction to boost the attention of my students	3.77	1.109	Moderately Agree
Overall	3.86	.928	Moderately Agree

Individually taken, the indicator participating in the courses/workshops to improve my preparation for the lesson on got the highest weighted mean of 3.93 and verbally interpreted as moderately agree. With the number of years invested in education, training, and practice prior to receiving a teaching license, a teacher must always be prepared for his or her vocation. However, whomever is assigned a task that is outside of their area of expertise may run into difficulties in completing it, just like a teacher who is given a subject that is out of his or her line of specialization. It would always take time to be prepared so as to deliver the lessons well in class and to be able to come up with activities where the learners can learn the subject effectively.

This result is in line with what was stated by Roffey (2017) that even teachers with the best preparation need help putting what they have learned into practice and transitioning from student teaching to their own classroom where they are now in charge. The difficulties are made worse for the growing number of teachers who enter classrooms without solid academic and professional

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preparation. Being prepared to teach the topic, particularly Physical Education, is one of the largest obstacles new teachers face, according to the research's regular conversations with instructors who did not major in MAPEH.

In addition, the indicator delivering a more interactive lesson to my students received a weighted mean of 3.92 (SD=1.002) and has a verbal interpretation of moderately agree. The students want to understand natural phenomena, to know scientific truths and to acquire knowledge to be applied in practice and for these reasons they are dissatisfied by the traditional education. This can be supported by the findings of the study conducted by Senthamaria (2018) which revealed that the teacher must employ heuristic, research, and strategies to promote discovery learning. He further revealed that the fundamental components of a recently established technique to stimulate learning, so that students and future engineers form a critical position towards the given content, are dynamic and communicative teaching methods, also known as interactive teaching methods. Lastly, he mentioned that the students' interest in the material is increased by using interactive methods and techniques.

Moreover, the indicator which obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.77 and SD of 1.109 and verbally interpreted as moretaley agree was utilizing media-based instruction to boost the attention of my students. The use of media in the classroom is what the learners need in this generation as they are called 21st century learners. This is congruent to what Mateer argued that teachers can engage students and produce more meaningful and deep learning experiences by using films, television shows, popular music, news stories, literature, documentaries, and videos from sources such as YouTube.

Table 7. Assessment of the Respondents on the Challenges They Encountered in Terms of Ongoing Teacher Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Participating in the courses/workshops to improve my preparation for the lesson.	3.93	.946	Moderately Agree
delivering a more interactive lesson to my students	3.92	1.002	Moderately Agree
integrating differentiated instruction in preparing my lesson.	3.90	1.000	Moderately Agree
providing technical assistance on students' behavior in the class	3.76	1.006	Moderately Agree
utilizing media-based instruction to boost the attention of my students	3.77	1.109	Moderately Agree
Overall	3.86	.928	Moderately Agree

The overall weighted mean of 3.77 (SD=.995) suggests a moderate agreement assessment of the respondents. Teachers are expected to teach a new subject sincethis is the focus of the locus of change in the field of education. This is one of the things that make teaching a challenging profession. According to Hobbs and Quinn (n.d.) teachers are often required to learn on the job and often without the support structure.

In addition, the statement maximize the time allotted in teaching my lesson obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.86 (SD=1.083) and has a verbal interpretation of moderately agree. Each subject is assigned with the so-called Budget of Work (BOW) that guides the teacher when to start and when to end a specific lesson. In this case, teachers should always maximize so that they can finish the lesson and that they can meet all the most essential learning competencies the learners must acquire at the end of every quarter. According to Department of Education (2023) the budget of work covers K–12 basic education curriculum competencies, skills, and objectives, subjects for certain skills and competencies; and teaching strategies, activities, and time allotment grouped into columns for simple reference and notation. It is a resource document for teachers of multi-grade classrooms teachers must use as a resource for creating daily and/or weekly lesson plans. The teachers who participated in the survey said that, on occasion, it can be challenging to make the most of the time given for each lesson because of unforeseen circumstances that have an impact on classroom activities and other curriculum-related activities.

Further, the statement conducts various research before planning the lesson achieved a weighted mean of 3.70 (SD=1.068) and verbally interpreted as moderately agree. Conducting research is one of the tasks that teachers usually. Research using a variety of references and speaking with knowledgeable teachers in the field, such as in MAPEH, could really help out-of-field teachers who know a bit about the subject deliver the lessons and prepare as well as execute the activities affectively. As stated by Bin-Hady (2018) teachers take necessary research-like steps for preparing lesson plans, such as reading the teaching materials for the lesson and listen to the cassette if it is connected with that lesson. Also, this finding is congruent with Morales argument which stated that in general, teachers are also researchers who must evaluate and assess their classroom activities in order to grow and improve their teaching as agents of knowledge and change.

As shared by the respondents, they continue to read books and visit websites where they can get ideas and information relevant to their classes because MAPEH is a new subject as it is outside of their field of competence. They added that in order to learn more about the lesson, they also asked their colleagues who have been teaching MAPEH for a longer time.

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Table 8. Assessment of the Respondents on the Challenges They Encountered in Terms of Formal Professional Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
<i>As a PE Teacher, I faced challenges in.....</i>			
welcoming the school head, master, or head teacher to observe my class for feedback giving	3.88	1.0	Agree
participating in collaborative discussions with my co-teachers in MAPEH	3.77	1.100	Agree
discussing strategy with my co-workers and mentors for unfamiliar topics/concepts to me	3.78	1.106	Agree
developing suggested teaching strategies from MAPEH mentors	3.79	1.028	Agree
following my mentor's advice to improve my personal and professional development in MAPEH teaching	3.71	1.131	Agree
Overall	3.79	1.004	Agree

It can be gleaned from Table 8 that the assessment of the respondents as to the challenges they encountered in terms of professional development has a composite mean of 3.79 and is verbally interpreted as agree. Teachers and educational institutions frequently respond by offering certification programs so non-specialist teachers can upskill, re-certify, or gain approval to teach a new subject. The respondents still view this as a challenge even though it is well-recognized that teaching is a career that necessitates ongoing training and development because they feel like they are returning to collegiate learning as they pick up new abilities and knowledge. Porsch and Whannell's (2015) claim to support the result as they said that subject-specific teacher preparation contributes to more efficient instruction and improved student competence.

The school head, master, or head teacher to observe my class for feedback gave the highest weighted mean of 3.88 (SD=1.047) and was verbally interpreted agree. According to RPMS, teachers must have at least two observations a year by which the school head, head teacher, or master teachers will provide technical assistance based on the observation. It is feasible to gauge how training initiatives and other interventions affect teachers and, in turn, how well students learn by monitoring teachers in the classroom. This result contradicts what Halim et al.'s investigation discovered. Because teachers learn and develop gradually with the aid of some practical approaches rather than being born with innate teaching abilities, all of which showed that teachers found observation to be a useful tool, it is well known that classroom observation is a powerful practical approach in both primary and higher education to help teachers improve their teaching quality.

On the one hand, the indicator following my mentor's advice to improve my personal and professional development in MAPEH teaching obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.71 and standard deviation of 1.131, which is verbally interpreted as agreed. Technical support is given to teachers to help them improve their instruction and, in turn, their pupils' learning. As a result, this difficulty is regarded as the least problem of the listed indicators. It is in line with the claim of Straus (2015) that teachers should be open to feedback, be active listeners, and be respectful of their mentor's input and time.

Table 9. Assessment of the Respondents on the Coping Strategies Utilized in Terms of Content Knowledge

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
<i>As a PE Teacher, I....</i>			
ask the assistance from co-teachers on how to apply knowledge of content within and across the curriculum teaching areas.	4.42	.781	Agree
weigh possible solutions for executing my activities in physical education	4.37	.720	Agree
choose to collaborate with my co-workers in creating performance tasks in PE	4.39	.751	Agree
acquire competence through training	4.45	.642	Agree
do watch fb live and video lesson	4.31	.825	Agree
Overall	4.39	.640	Agree

It can be seen from Table 9 that the overall mean for the coping strategies that the respondents utilized as to content knowledge is 4.39 (SD=.640) and has a verbal interpretation of agree. Given their status as out-of-field teachers, they must seek assistance from others, especially mentors and more experienced co-workers like those with a MAPEH major.

Individually taken, the statement acquire competence through training received the highest weighted mean of 4.45 and was verbally interpreted as agree. Teachers must train before entering the classroom and receive ongoing training even as they work there. Teachers must be given the greatest chance of success and sustain veteran teachers as they meet new educational challenges, especially those given teaching loads out of their specialization. The result is synonymous with Horizon Report (2016) that one of the immediate recommendations was the need for teacher education programs to reconceptualize training to more closely address the skill set needed by the 21st-century educator.

According to Srirat (2017), Facebook is one of the most popular social networking websites, which allows users to share and exchange profiles, photos, and videos with others. It can be a useful tool in teaching various subjects. With the demand of

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21st-century learning, where technology dominates, they are usually motivated to listen and watch when the lessons are delivered via FB live. More so, Carag (2020) supports this finding as he found out in his study that as a provider of knowledge, teachers in MAPEH may use technology as an innovative tool for improving the quality teaching-learning process and may participate in a seminar-workshop for them to enhance their teaching capabilities as mentors.

Table 10. Assessment of the Respondents on the Coping Strategies Utilized in Terms of Context-Specific Pedagogical Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
make a plan of action and try to carry it out	4.34	.755	Agree
assess students' Performance in Physical Education	4.44	.686	Agree
communicate well with other MAPEH teachers to get skills as to how to teach the subject	4.46	.673	Agree
provide a variety of concrete learning materials in teaching Physical Education	4.39	.695	Agree
Design, organize and select formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements	4.41	.726	Agree
Overall	4.41	.623	Agree

As shown in Table 10, the respondents agreed to utilize the indicated coping strategies, as shown in the obtained overall mean and standard deviation of 4.41 and .623, respectively. The result indicates that out-of-field teachers continue to adjust to give the learning the students deserve. According to Carag (2020), it is important to note how teachers employ because doing so helps students receive a high-quality education. It is now the responsibility of the knowledge supplier to disclose the methods used to keep track of the types of students in the classroom.

Obtaining the highest mean of 4.46 (SD=.673) and verbal interpretation of agree is communicated well with other MAPEH teachers to learn how to teach the subject. This means that out-of-field teachers do not disregard the significance of communication in an academic institution. Communication and collaboration among teachers lead to school improvement and student success because it allows teachers to delegate tasks that allow each to feel effective and fosters the development of significant professional and personal relationships. It also allows non-major teachers to get additional information and improve their knowledge about the lessons they will deliver in class.

Based on the Department of Education (DepEd) Memorandum Number 050 series 2020 contains the professional development for teachers priorities for the school years 2020-2023, a variety of efficient diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment procedures that are in line with curriculum requirements must be designed, selected, organized, and used by teachers in collaboration with colleagues.

Table 11. Assessment of the Respondents on the Coping Strategies Utilized in Terms of Careful Guidance

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Invite the school head, master, or head teacher to observe my class and provide technical assistance	4.15	.833	Agree
Participate in collaborative discussions with my co-teachers in MAPEH and other learning areas	4.41	.698	Agree
Discuss my strategy with my co-workers and mentors for any unfamiliar content	4.39	.665	Agree
Follow my mentors' advice in strengthening my MAPEH teaching strategies.	4.41	.712	Agree
Apply my mentor's advice to improve my personal and professional development in teaching MAPEH.	4.46	.642	Agree
Overall	4.36	.608	Agree

Table 11 reveals that the respondents agreed that they utilized careful guidance as one of the strategies as out-of-field teachers as it obtained an overall mean of 4.36, standard deviation of .608. This finding suggests that non-specialist teachers are consulting those who have more experience. It is quite helpful to get technical support or guidance from mentors, school administrators, head teachers, master teachers, and subject-matter experts. It is congruent with Mott (2015), stating that professional teachers learn through different modes. One is learning in the inquiry mode, which is exploratory and cooperative, and produces a synthesis or creation of new techniques or concepts.

When viewed separately, applying my mentor's advice to improve my personal and professional development in teaching MAPEH obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.46 and verbally interpreted as agree. Technical assistance provided by the mentors should be applied in the class, particularly in delivering the lessons. The result can be supported by Strauss et al. (2015) as he cited that teachers as mentees should be open to feedback, be active listeners, and be respectful of their mentor's input and time.

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Lastly, the item that got the lowest weighted mean of 4.15 but was still verbally interpreted as agree is inviting the school head, master, or head teacher to observe my class and provide technical assistance. It might be the case since the RPMS mandates that teachers provide technical support to observers rather than inviting them in. There are two schedules for classroom observations per year, one (1) for each semester. The school principal distributes a link so that teachers can enter their preferred schedule for classroom observation.

Table 12. Assessment of the Respondents on the Coping Strategies Utilized in Terms of Attentive Leadership

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
know how to establish and maintain professional relationships with my superiors, co-workers, and students	4.49	.643	Agree
tend to overcome barriers to reach my goals	4.34	.685	Agree
seek out additional information from the school leader, teacher, or some other source	4.48	.559	Agree
Welcome others to challenge my ideas and strategies constantly	4.35	.672	Agree
seek feedback as a way of understanding myself as a teacher	4.45	.702	Agree
Overall	4.42	.563	Agree

The attained composite mean of 4.42 (SD=.563) suggests that the respondents agreed on attentive leadership as a strategy for out-of-field teachers. It means the respondents deeply understand their strengths and shortcomings and know how they manifest in their interactions. It could also mean the respondents know how to manage their weaknesses properly. The result is consistent with Walt (2018) when he stated that attentive leaders intimately know their strengths and weaknesses and how they are expressed in their behavior towards others. He also stated that authentic leaders can thoughtfully compensate for their weaknesses and manage them wisely.

As agreed, obtaining the highest mean of 4.49 (SD=.643) is knowing how to establish and maintain a professional relationship with my superiors, co-workers, and students. However, if there is one job where maintaining harmonious relationships among professionals is crucial, it is teaching. Meador (2019) supports this finding by suggesting that professionalism is a quality every educator and school employee should possess. Also, Cassiatori (2021) cited that effective teachers form authentic, caring relationships with their students. He further stated that a healthy relationship between the teachers and stakeholders is important, enabling everybody to work together and positively impacting the students harmoniously.

Moreover, the item tended to overcome barriers to reach my goals and attained the lowest weighted mean of 4.33 and standard deviation of .685. It suggests that even out-of-field teacher-respondents always find ways to overcome the challenges they face in teaching MAPEH subjects. It is consistent with what the respondents said, who admitted that there are times when they are unsure of whether the materials they produce for the students are accurate and would help them achieve proficiency. They view them as teachers, and professionalism must always be upheld.

Table 13. Level of Performance of the Respondents in Terms of Human Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
I enthusiastically learn about the different aspects of teaching Physical Education from my co-workers	4.37	.706	Agree
I am aware that I need to study the lessons with understanding so that I can deliver them to the class successfully	4.60	.620	Strongly Agree
I seek suggestions from MAPEH major teachers to deepen my knowledge and enhance my skills	4.56	.671	Strongly Agree
I creatively design the lesson for better discussion and interaction	4.38	.708	Agree
I take the suggestion of my superiors and co-workers constructively.	4.49	.643	Agree
Overall	4.48	.571	Agree

Table 13 shows the respondent's assessment of the level of human skills. These are also known as soft skills or interpersonal skills. Generally, the respondents' assessment of their human skills obtained an overall mean of 4.48 (SD=.571) and was verbally interpreted as agree. It can be assumed that the respondents can establish positive relationships with others and possess motivation, enthusiasm, and effective listening and writing abilities.

Individually taken, I need to study the lessons with understanding to successfully deliver them to the class, receiving the highest computed weighted mean of 4.60 and a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Teaching is a never-ending process. Teachers should also study their lessons if pupils are expected to because effective teaching is required. In addition, I enthusiastically learned about the different aspects of teaching Physical Education from my co-workers, got the lowest weighted

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mean of 4.38, a standard deviation of .706, and a verbal interpretation of agree. As mentioned in the previous results, out-of-field teachers consult with mentors and maintain communication with other teachers, particularly experts in the field. In this case, they can learn beyond their knowledge relative to teaching MAPEH.

Table 14. Level of Performance of the Respondents in Terms of Hard Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
I enthusiastically learn about the different aspects of teaching Physical Education from my co-workers	4.37	.706	Agree
I am aware that I need to study the lessons with understanding so that I can deliver them to the class successfully	4.60	.620	Strongly Agree
I seek suggestions from MAPEH major teachers to deepen my knowledge and enhance my skills	4.56	.671	Strongly Agree
I creatively design the lesson for better discussion and interaction	4.38	.708	Agree
I take the suggestion of my superiors and co-workers constructively.	4.49	.643	Agree
Overall	4.48	.571	Agree

Table 14 indicates that the overall mean of the hard skill of the respondents is 4.47 (SD=.598) and has a verbal interpretation of agree. Hard skills for MAPEH teachers are those abilities and competencies that are required to effectively and efficiently instruct students. Even though the respondents are out-of-field teachers, they make it a point that they can still do their part as MAPEH teachers. For example, the indicator keeps and evaluates my student's performance records in MAPEH obtained a weighted mean of 4.52 and was verbally interpreted as strongly agree. On the one hand, the item that got the lowest weighted mean is providing feedback to my learners and planning and implementing a developmentally sequenced teaching and learning process to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts. Curriculum requirements must be met at the end of the school year.

The results are the same one the point of Phelps (2019), who stated that the Hard skills of educators also involve the ability to understand student needs, develop course objectives and assessments, create instructional strategies, establish effective learning environments, assess learning outcomes, evaluate student performance, provide feedback on student progress, collaborate with colleagues on educational initiatives.

Table 15. Level of Self-Efficacy of the Respondents

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
align my lesson plan with the essential learning competency and follow the budget of work	4.46	.688	Agree
keep and evaluate my student's records of their performances in MAPEH	4.52	.659	Strongly Agree
provide feedback on my learner's Performance	4.43	.685	Agree
plan and implement developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts	4.43	.655	Agree
Integrate technology in teaching MAPEH	4.49	.659	Agree
Overall	4.47	.598	Agree

Apart from being a good indicator of teachers' effectiveness, teachers' self-efficacy is essential for an effective school and academic program. The process of restructuring schools and establishing effective schools are believed to be determined by the teachers' self-efficacy, which is an important variable that must be considered.

It can be gleaned from the table that the overall level of the respondents' performance in terms of self-efficacy is 4.38 (SD=.563) and verbally interpreted as agree. It indicates that despite the respondents being given subjects that are out of the area of their expertise, they still believe that they can somehow teach their students well. The respondents confirmed during the usual conversation with the researcher that during the first days of handling the subject, they had low self-efficacy and were not motivated because they had to study a new set of subjects. About the findings of Hobbs and Porsch (2021), the result of out-of-field teaching promotes learning opportunities, and the experience of educators teaching the subject multiple times caused an increase in educators' perceived capacity. Experience leads to improved confidence among out-of-field educators. This result is also congruent with the findings of Kini and Podolsky (2016), which showed that as educators gain experience, their students learn more and are more likely to do better in school attendance.

The results also revealed that inspiring the learners to produce meaningful concepts and worthwhile performance got the highest weighted mean of 4.46 and was verbally interpreted as agree. Despite the difficulty that they are also new to the subject they are teaching, teachers are very much dedicated to ensuring quality education by doing their best to help students learn and

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understand even the most difficult lessons. It is further supported by the study of Co et al. (2021), stating that a teacher's attitude concerning teaching subjects outside their specialization is vital for effective teaching. Lastly, the item making plans when, where, and how to reach my goals got the lowest weighted mean of 4.31 and was verbally interpreted as agree. As out-of-field teachers, they aim to teach the subject well and handle the learners effectively. The commitment of teachers encompasses their enthusiasm to accept the challenge of teaching subjects outside of their specialization (Co et al., 2021). It was also supported by the teachers' response when they shared that they feel a sense of achievement despite their challenges if the students tell them how grateful they are for the lesson learned from their subject.

Table16: Level of Self-Efficacy of the Respondents

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
managing my time in accomplishing various tasks	4.34	.623	Agree
making plans when, where, and how to reach my goals	4.31	.662	Agree
looking for new solutions to address unavoidable circumstances	4.40	.586	Agree
promoting interactive learning to bring out the desired outcomes of the students	4.42	.622	Agree
remaining calm despite the challenges I encountered	4.35	.702	Agree
establishing attainable performance for better engagement	4.35	.657	Agree
encouraging and supporting my learners in making their own sound decisions	4.40	.667	Agree
inspiring the learners to produce meaningful concepts and worthwhile Performance	4.46	.626	Agree
evaluating, recognizing, and valuing the outcomes of my actions	4.40	.636	Agree
handling unprecedented situations and stressful environment	4.33	.682	Agree
Overall	4.38	.563	Agree

The overall level of the respondents' performance in terms of self-efficacy is 4.38 (SD=.563) and verbally interpreted as agree.

Table 16. Significant Relationship Between Challenges, Coping Strategies, And Self-Efficacy

Challenges	Self-Efficacy
The transition from initial teacher education to novice	.134
Ongoing teacher learning	.098
Formal professional development	.037
Coping Strategies	
Content Knowledge	.578**
Context-Specific Pedagogical Skills	.727**
Careful Guidance	.695**
Attentive Leadership	.711**

It can be seen from Table 16 that there is a significant relationship between coping strategies and self-efficacy variables. On the one hand, a moderate to strong relationship is seen between variables.

Every teacher is expected to perform certain roles in the workplace. And the performance of those expected roles depends upon an individual's belief about his capacity to perform those roles effectively. Nevertheless, some teachers are given tasks that were not part of their previous training, such as the case of out-of-field teachers. The challenge for them is how they would believe they can teach the subjects well and figure out what coping they can use to overcome the challenges. The result shows a moderately significant relationship between the respondents' coping strategies and self-efficacy variables. Jex et al. (2016) support the finding in which he argues that individuals with high self-efficacy confidently believe in their abilities to respond to the environment stimulus and maintain self-control effectively. Salanova (2015) also considered self-efficacy a dominant organizational catalyst that can help develop actions and effective strategies (active coping strategies) for defeating or mitigating the issues caused by the educational factors that affect teachers' performances.

Rosenbaum (1990) presented a theory of learned resourcefulness that suggested that individuals who are rich in resourcefulness can cope better with stress than those who are poor. They achieve this result by minimizing the negative consequences of stress.

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Table 17. Significant Relationship Between Challenges, Coping Strategies, And Self-Performance

Challenges	Performance	
	Human Skills	Hard Skill
The transition from initial teacher education to novice	.139	.092
Ongoing teacher learning	.112	.112
Formal professional development	.117	-.001
Coping Strategies		
Content Knowledge	.639**	.533**
Context-Specific Pedagogical Skills	.731**	.667**
Careful Guidance	.723**	.705**
Attentive Leadership	.754**	.754**

There is a significant relationship between coping strategies and performance variables. Moderate to strong relationship was seen between the variables. As Gustems-Carnicer et al. (2019) cited, teachers should be given ample space to relieve stress through coping strategies and improve themselves as indispensable catalysts of the academic environment. Like other professionals, teachers experience stress and use avoidance of coping strategies, affecting their performance in the workplace.

Table 18. Mediating Effect of Self-Efficacy Between Coping Strategies and Performance

Indirect Effects	Effect	SE	LLCI	ULCI
C→SE→P	.0481	.0569	-.0448	.1790
CS→SE→P	.3749	.0918	.2043	.5586
Completely Standardized Indirect Effects				
C→SE→P	.0791	.0860	-.0812	.2501
CS→SE→P	.3735	.0832	.2151	.5448

Mediation analyses were initiated using PROCESS Macro v4.1 following the procedure of Hayes (2022). Findings revealed that Self-Efficacy constructs do not mediate the relationship between Challenges and Performance. On the other hand, Self-Efficacy could explain the variations in Coping Strategies and Performance Scores. These indirect effects are statistically different from zero, as revealed by a biased-corrected bootstrap confidence interval based on 5,000 samples from the lower and upper limit class interval. The result indicates that overall Self-Efficacy can transmit the effect of being influenced by Coping Strategies, increasing performance. It can also be noticed that overall Self-Efficacy demonstrated the highest mediating effect of Coping Strategies on Performance (CS=.3749). This indirect effect means that respondents who differ by one unit in their reported Coping Strategies are estimated to vary by 37.35% units on the performance. The results further explain that for those with relatively higher Coping Strategies, realizing their Self-Efficacy later translates into greater Performance.

The result is synonymous with the definition of self-efficacy provided by Schwarzer and Hallum (2016) that it is the perceived competence of the teacher to cope with all challenges and hassles accumulated with their career. Also, Pethe and Chaudhari (2016) stated that an individual with higher self-efficacy believes that he can perform organizational tasks.

V. CONCLUSIONS

1. Majority of the respondents were female, 26-30 years old, attained a bachelor's Degree, Filipino major, and had been in the teaching profession for 0-3 years.
2. The respondents assessed all the indicated challenges to a moderate degree.
3. The respondents also rated agreeing with all the indicated coping strategies.
4. The level of performance of the respondents as too hard and human skills were both rated agree by the respondents, which means a high-level performance.
5. The respondents rated the level of self-efficacy agree, implying true of me assessment.
6. There is a significant relationship between coping strategies and self-efficacy variables. On the one hand, a moderate to strong relationship was seen between variables. Thus, the research null hypothesis is accepted.
7. There is a significant relationship between coping strategies and performance variables. A moderate to strong relationship was seen between variables; hence, the research null hypothesis is partially sustained.
8. Self-Efficacy does not mediate the relationship between Challenges and Performance. It led to the acceptance of the research null hypothesis.

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